

THE PREVALENCE OF PREMENSTRUAL SYNDROME AND ITS ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS AMONG YOUNG FEMALES OF UNIVERSITY OF LAHORE

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Abstract

Background: Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) is a combination of physical and emotional symptoms, these symptoms start from 1 to 2 weeks before menstruation, before the onset of menstrual flow, these symptoms occur in cyclic pattern. Premenstrual symptoms are more prevalent and severe in highly educated women than in uneducated women, and there may be a link between stress and PMS. PMS involves psychiatric or physical symptoms that severely affect a woman's ability to function normally in daily life, including at work, in relationships, and with personal activities, ultimately diminishing her overall quality of life. PMS is a significant health issue for young girls because it is common in younger age groups. Premenstrual syndrome and premenstrual dysphoric disorder can be treated with lifestyle measures such as physical exercise, quitting smoking, and weight control.

Objective: The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of premenstrual syndrome (PMS) within university students, as well as the risk factors related with PMS.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among young females at the University of Lahore to determine the prevalence of premenstrual syndrome (PMS) and its associated risk factors. A total of 383 participants of female university students with regular menstrual cycle aged between 18-30 years, currently not pregnant nor breastfeeding were recruited using a convenient sampling technique. Females with diagnosed depression, any gynecological problem, taking hormonal therapy and those did not complete the questionnaire were excluded. Data collection involved administering a structured questionnaire, which included two sections: The Premenstrual Symptoms Screening Tool (PSST) is used to assess PMS and a demographic form to evaluate potential risk factors.

Results: The prevalence of PMS was 62.4%. If we discuss about potential risk factors participants with underweight 30(7.8%), healthy weight 174(45.5%), over weight 88(23%), obese 91(23.8%), physical activity > 150 min per week 63(16.4%), physical activity < 150 min per week 204(53.3%), no physical activity 116(30.3%), consumption of fruits and vegetables < 5 times a week 234(61.1%), consumption of junk food < 5 times a week 149(38.9%), depression

91(23.8%),hypothyroidism 62(16.2%),hyperthyroidism 44(11.5%),no health problem 186(48.6%). The chi-square analysis revealed that age ($p = 0.001$), BMI ($p = 0.001$), physical activity ($p = 0.001$), nutritional status ($p = 0.001$), and health status ($p = 0.001$) had a statistically significant association with PMS.

Conclusion: The research revealed a high prevalence of Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) within young females. Age, BMI, physical activity, nutritional status, and health status were strongly connected with PMS.

INTRODUCTION

Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) is a combination of physical and psychological symptoms, starting from 1 to 2 weeks before menstruation, before the onset of menstrual flow, these symptoms occur in cyclic pattern. The World Health Organization estimates that between 20 and 31 percent of female university students globally suffer from at least one mental illness related to menstruation. However, prevalence statistics vary greatly across research and nations, based on diagnostic standards and research techniques. PMS have recently gained significant interest in the research community due to their high global prevalence. PMS affects students' quality of life (QoL) more than is suggested and stated since they typically ignore its symptoms. During regular check-ups, medical professionals should be aware of PMS.

Premenstrual symptoms are more prevalent and severe in highly educated women than in uneducated women, and there may be a link between stress and PMS. Because PMS symptoms frequently coexist with anxiety and other psychological symptoms, they cause serious psychosocial dysfunctions. PMS is a significant health issue for young girls because it is common in younger age groups.(Rezende et al., 2022) Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) occurs during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle and typically subsides on its own once menstruation begins. Although the cause of PMS is yet unknown, certain women's vulnerability to the typical hormonal fluctuations that take place during the menstrual cycle is linked to the symptoms.

There is compelling evidence linking ovulation inhibitors to cyclic ovarian activity since they frequently alleviate premenstrual symptoms both during pregnancy and after menopause. So that, we conducted a research To find out how common premenstrual syndrome (PMS) are among university students, as well as the causes of PMS, the most

common symptoms, and how symptoms affect social, professional, familial, and academic activities. Finding PMS risk factors is crucial to preventing symptoms and lessening the syndrome's effects. The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of premenstrual syndrome (PMS) within university students, as well as the risk factors related with PMS. Dinh Trieu Ngo Vy et al. studied potential aspects related to Premenstrual Syndrome and Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder. The literature has extensively documented the impact of PMS and PMDD on women's quality of life. Menarche age, coffee intake, self-reported depression, and negative Rhesus blood type were the main risk factors for premenstrual syndrome and premenstrual dysphoric disorder.(Dinh Trieu Ngo et al., 2023) Lee, Wanhyung, et al. studied the Premenstrual syndrome incidence rate and risk factors among the working population in the Republic of Korea. This cohort's objective is to present the prevalence and pertinent risk factors of PMS in Korean female employees who are of reproductive age. This study uses a follow-up design to examine the PMS status, trends, and risk factors among women in the middle-aged working population. Further research is needed to gain a better knowledge of the risk factors for PMS among reproductive-aged female workers. (Lee, Lee, Ahn, Lee, & Kang, 2022)

Methodology:

A cross-sectional study was conducted among young females at the University of Lahore to determine the prevalence of premenstrual syndrome (PMS) and its associated risk factors. A total of 383 participants were recruited using a convenient sampling technique. Data collection involved administering a structured questionnaire, which included two sections: The Premenstrual Symptoms Screening Tool (PSST) to assess PMS and a demographic form

to evaluate potential risk factors. The demographic form gathered information on participants' age, body mass index (BMI), overall health status, nutritional status, and physical activity levels. The PSST questionnaire was used to categorize the severity of PMS symptoms and identify individuals meeting the diagnostic criteria. Before data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring ethical considerations were met. The questionnaire was distributed in both online and paper-based formats to facilitate accessibility and encourage participation. Participants were given clear instructions on completing the questionnaire, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the study. The collected data were then compiled and analyzed to determine the prevalence of PMS and its association with the identified risk factors.

Results:

We collected the data from 383 female students, 63 (16.4%) were between the ages of 18 and 23, 200 (52.2%) were between the ages of 22 and 25, and 120 (31.3%) were between the ages of 26 and 30. If we discuss about potential risk factors participants with underweight 30(7.8%), healthy weight 174(45.5%),over weight 88(23%),obese 91(23.8%),physical activity > 150 min per week 63(16.4%), physical activity < 150 min per week 204(53.3%),no physical activity 116(30.3%), consumption of fruits and vegetables < 5 times a

week 234(61.1%),consumption of junk food < 5 times a week 149(38.9%),depression 91(23.8%),hypothyroidism 62(16.2%),hyperthyroidism 44(11.5%),no health problem 186(48.6%).

If we talk about symptoms, the majority of the participants 153 (39.9%) had moderate anger/irritability, 185 (48.3%) had moderate anxiety/tension, 129 (33.7%) had moderate tearful/Increased sensitivity to rejection, 196 (51.2%) felt moderate decreased mood/hopelessness, 208 (54.3%) had moderate decreased interest in work activities, 196 (51.2%) had moderate decreased interest in social activities, 218 (56.9%) had moderate difficulty concentrating, 143 (37.3%) had moderate fatigue/lack of energy, 140 (37.3%) had moderate food craving/overate, 125 (32.6%) had moderate insomnia, 122 (31.9%) had moderate hypersomnia, 125 (32.6%) had moderate feeling of overwhelmed or out of control, 153 (39.9%) had moderate physical symptoms: breast tenderness, headaches, joint/muscle pain, bloating, weight gain. According to the symptoms, the majority of females 153 (39.9%) had moderate word efficiency or productivity, 153 (39.9%) said symptoms moderately interfered with their relationships with coworkers, 168 (43.9%) said symptoms moderately interfered with their relationships with family and 168 (43.9%) said symptoms moderately interfered with home responsibilities.

		PMS		
		present	absent	p-value
Age	18-21 years	17 (4.4%)	46 (12%0	0.001
	22-25 years	163 (42.6%)	37 (9.7%)	
	26-30 years	59 (15.4%)	61 (15.9%)	
BMI	Underweight	21 (5.5%)	9 (2.3%)	0.001
	Healthy Weight	52 (13.6%)	122 (31.9%)	
	Overweight	88 (23%)	0	
	Obese	78 (20.4%)	13 (3.4%)	
Physical Activity	> 150 min per week	58 (15.1%)	5 (1.3%0	0.001
	< 150 min per week	65 (17%)	139 (36.3%)	
	none	116 (30.3%)	0	
Nutritional Status	Consumption of fruits and vegetables< 5 times a week	90 (23.5%)	144 (37.6%)	0.001
	Consumption of junk food< 5 times a week	149 (38.9%)	0	
Health Status	Depression	75 (19.6%)	16 (4.2%)	0.001

	Hypothyroidism	62 (16.2%)	0
	Hyperthyroidism	44 (11.5%)	0
	None	58 (15.1%)	128 (33.4%)

Table shows cross tabulation and chi square analysis between associated risk factors and premenstrual syndrome

Discussion:

Younger females, those with lower BMI, higher physical activity, and better nutrition were less likely to experience PMS. Conversely, poor nutrition, higher BMI, and health conditions like depression and thyroid disorders were linked to higher PMS prevalence. These findings suggest the importance of addressing modifiable risk factors such as physical activity and nutrition in managing PMS. The findings current study reveals a high prevalence of PMS (62.4%) among the participants, which is consistent with global trends. Previous studies have reported varying prevalence rates of PMS, ranging from thirty percent to ninety percent, depending on the population studied, diagnostic criteria, and methodology. For example, research conducted among university students in Iran revealed a PMS prevalence rate of 70.8% (A, K, A, & Sattar, 2014), while a separate study in Turkey documented an even higher prevalence of 75.8% (Yonkers, O'Brien, & Eriksson, 2008). These findings are consistent with the results of the current study, which identified a prevalence rate of 62.4% among young females at the University of Lahore. The similarity in prevalence rates across these diverse populations underscores the widespread nature of PMS, particularly among young women in academic environments. University settings often expose students to unique stressors, such as academic demands, social pressures, and lifestyle challenges, which may contribute to the exacerbation of PMS symptoms. The high prevalence observed in these studies suggests that PMS is a significant public health concern among young females, warranting further attention and targeted interventions to address the underlying risk factors and improve quality of life.

The study highlighted age as a significant factor linked to PMS, with the largest proportion of participants falling within the 22-25 age group, accounting for 52.2% of the sample. Younger women may be more susceptible to experiencing

pronounced PMS symptoms due to a combination of hormonal changes and psychosocial stressors, such as the demands of academic life, social expectations, and the transitional nature of this life stage. However, it is important to note that some studies have reported a higher prevalence of PMS among older age groups, indicating that the relationship between age and PMS is not entirely straightforward and may vary depending on factors such as the population studied, cultural influences, and lifestyle differences. This variability suggests that while younger women may be at a higher risk for PMS in certain contexts, the condition can also significantly affect older women, emphasizing the need for a nuanced understanding of how age interacts with other contributing factors in the manifestation of PMS symptoms.

The implications of the current study highlight the need for targeted interventions. Healthcare providers should prioritize screening, especially for those with risk factors like obesity, sedentary behavior, and poor diet. Lifestyle modifications, such as regular exercise, balanced nutrition, and stress management, should be promoted as first-line strategies. Mental health support must also be integrated into PMS care due to its strong link with depression and anxiety. Educational programs to raise awareness about PMS and its risk factors can empower young females to seek timely care and adopt preventive measures, improving their overall well-being.

Conclusion:

The study found a high prevalence of Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) (62.4%) among young females at the University of Lahore. Age, BMI, physical activity, nutritional status, and health status were significantly associated with PMS. Younger females, those with lower BMI, higher physical activity, and better nutrition were less likely to experience PMS. Conversely, poor nutrition, higher BMI, and health conditions like depression and thyroid disorders were linked to higher PMS prevalence. These findings suggest the importance of addressing modifiable risk factors such as physical activity and nutrition in managing PMS.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Future researchers can conduct longitudinal studies to better understand the causal relationships between PMS and its associated risk factors, such as age, BMI, physical activity, and dietary habits.
- Future studies can explore the role of cultural and socioeconomic factors in the prevalence and severity of PMS across diverse populations.
- Future researchers can assess the effectiveness of specific lifestyle interventions, such as tailored exercise programs or dietary plans, in reducing PMS symptoms.
- Future studies can incorporate the examination of the impact of mental health interventions, including cognitive-behavioral therapy or mindfulness practices, on PMS-related emotional and psychological symptoms.

LIMITATIONS

- The study relied on self-reported data, which may introduce recall bias or inaccuracies in participants' responses regarding symptoms, lifestyle habits, and health conditions.
- The sample was limited to young females from a single university, which may restrict the generalizability of findings to other populations or age groups.
- The study did not consider the potential impact of occupational factors, such as work environment or job stress, on PMS symptoms.

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